

RESPONSE PAPER 6**LAST NAME: BANGURA****FIRST NAME: FODAY SORIE****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: PROF.GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is the function of footnotes in academic writing, according to Turabian?
 - To provide additional analysis or commentary on a key argument.
 - To document sources and provide supplemental information without disrupting the text.¹**
 - To summarize key points made in the main text for readers unfamiliar with the topic.
 - To create a visual break between sections of the argument for readability.
2. According to Turabian, which of the following is the most effective strategy for integrating direct quotations into a paper?

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th Ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 55.

- Using them extensively in place of original writing.
 - Introducing them with context and commentary while ensuring they support the argument.²**
 - Quoting large blocks of text to demonstrate thorough research.
 - Embedding them without explanation, lets the readers infer their significance.
3. According to Bloomberg and Volpe, how should researchers approach coding in qualitative data analysis?
- By using only pre-determined codes based on the literature review.
 - By creating flexible codes derived from the data, reflective of emerging patterns.³**
 - By avoiding software tools to maintain the authenticity of the analysis.
 - By coding only data that directly supports the researcher's hypothesis.
4. What is the role of reflective journaling in qualitative research, according to Bloomberg and Volpe?
- To record personal thoughts unrelated to the study.
 - To document the researcher's biases, assumptions, and reactions to data collection and analysis.⁴**
 - To organize participants' responses systematically.

² Ibid., 75.

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE, 2019), 193.

⁴ Ibid., 121.

- To provide a narrative summary of the methodology chapter.
5. According to Sampson, what is the primary role of the research problem in a dissertation?
- To outline the anticipated findings of the study.
- To provide a clear, concise statement that justifies the need for the research.**⁵
- To summarize the methodological approach in advance.
- To serve as a placeholder until the research questions are finalized.
6. According to Sampson, how should a researcher frame their literature review in a dissertation?
- As a comprehensive analysis that positions the study within existing research and identifies gaps.**⁶
- As a chronological summary of studies in the field.
- As an opportunity to critique methodologies without connecting them to the research problem.
- As a detailed replication of the study's findings from prior research.
7. What is the fundamental purpose of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course as outlined in the coursepack?
- To introduce students to advanced methodologies in qualitative research.

⁵ James P. Sampson. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee, FL: Florida State University, 2017), 8.

⁶ Ibid., 31.

- To cultivate a foundational understanding of scholarly research and academic writing.**⁷
- To explore the ethical dimensions of academic research.
- To provide technical training in data analysis software for dissertation research.
8. In the ACA-401/ACA-401D framework, what is the recommended approach to structuring an academic paper?
- Begin with a detailed literature review, followed by research methodology, results, and conclusion.
- Follow a logical progression of introduction, argumentation, and synthesis while adhering to institutional guidelines.**⁸
- Adopt a thematic structure, grouping findings under key themes regardless of research focus.
- Begin with methodology and incorporate the literature review into the discussion section.
9. What does the English Style Guide recommend regarding the use of abbreviations in text?
- Avoid abbreviations entirely to maintain formal tone.
- Use abbreviations freely, as long as they are not defined in the text.
- Define abbreviations on first use and avoid overuse to ensure clarity.**⁹

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, 5th ed.* (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University, 2024), 7.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 15.

- Place a comprehensive list of abbreviations at the beginning of the document.

10. How does the English Style Guide suggest handling quotations in texts?

- Use single quotation marks for all quotes, regardless of length.
- Enclose short quotations in double quotation marks, and use block formatting for longer quotes¹⁰.**
- Incorporate all quotes into the main text, regardless of length or formatting.
- Avoid using direct quotations to maintain a cohesive voice in the text.

⁹ European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed., (European Commission, 2021), 23.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 35.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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